

Appendix

Appendix (A) Variable Descriptive(s)

Performance Goal Orientation

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Performance_Orientation	184	100.0%	0	0.0%	184	100.0%

Descriptives

		Statistic	Std. Error	
Performance_Orientation	Mean	43.9348	.48343	
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	42.9810	
		Upper Bound	44.8886	
	5% Trimmed Mean	44.2633		
	Median	45.0000		
	Variance	43.001		
	Std. Deviation	6.55753		
	Minimum	23.00		
	Maximum	56.00		
	Range	33.00		
	Interquartile Range	9.00		
	Skewness	-.765	.179	
	Kurtosis	.245	.356	

Neuroticism

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Neuroticism	184	100.0%	0	0.0%	184	100.0%

Descriptives

		Statistic	Std. Error	
Neuroticism	Mean	56.5978	1.02369	
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	54.5781	
		Upper Bound	58.6176	
	5% Trimmed Mean	56.3998		
	Median	56.5000		
	Variance	192.821		
	Std. Deviation	13.88600		
	Minimum	20.00		
	Maximum	93.00		
	Range	73.00		
	Interquartile Range	20.00		
	Skewness	.176	.179	
	Kurtosis	-.208	.356	

Extrinsic Motivation

Case Processing Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Extrinsic_Motivation	184	100.0%	0	0.0%	184	100.0%

Descriptives

		Statistic	Std. Error	
Extrinsic_Motivation	Mean	13.0163	.25947	
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	12.5044	
		Upper Bound	13.5282	
	5% Trimmed Mean	13.0616		
	Median	13.0000		
	Variance	12.388		
	Std. Deviation	3.51962		
	Minimum	4.00		
	Maximum	20.00		
	Range	16.00		
	Interquartile Range	5.00		
	Skewness	-.278	.179	
	Kurtosis	-.332	.356	

Sense of Mattering

Case Processing Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Sense_Mattering	184	100.0%	0	0.0%	184	100.0%

Descriptives

		Statistic	Std. Error	
Sense_Mattering	Mean	89.9022	1.06481	
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	87.8013	
		Upper Bound	92.0031	
	5% Trimmed Mean	90.2935		
	Median	91.0000		
	Variance	208.624		
	Std. Deviation	14.44383		
	Minimum	44.00		
	Maximum	120.00		
	Range	76.00		
	Interquartile Range	22.00		
	Skewness	-.426	.179	
	Kurtosis	.148	.356	

Career Satisfaction

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Career_Satisfaction	184	100.0%	0	0.0%	184	100.0%

Descriptives

		Statistic	Std. Error	
Career_Satisfaction	Mean	17.4022	.34130	
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	16.7288	
		Upper Bound	18.0756	
	5% Trimmed Mean	17.6232		
	Median	18.0000		
	Variance	21.433		
	Std. Deviation	4.62958		
	Minimum	5.00		
	Maximum	25.00		
	Range	20.00		
	Interquartile Range	5.00		
	Skewness	-.761	.179	
	Kurtosis	.375	.356	

Appendix (B) Tests of Normality and Histograms

Performance goal orientation

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Performance_Orientation	.118	184	.000	.954	184	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Neuroticism

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Neuroticism	.061	184	.097	.993	184	.566

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Extrinsic Motivation

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Extrinsic_Motivation	.104	184	.000	.979	184	.006

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Sense of Mattering

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Sense_Mattering	.073	184	.019	.982	184	.017

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Career Satisfaction

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Career_Satisfaction	.138	184	.000	.942	184	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Appendix (C) Boxplots (with Outliers)

Performance Goal Orientation

Neuroticism

Extrinsic Motivation

Sense of Mattering

Career Satisfaction

Appendix (D) Normal Q-Q plots

Performance Goal Orientation

Neuroticism

Extrinsic Motivation

Sense of Meaning

Career Satisfaction

Appendix (E) Scatterplots With best line of fit

PGO and CS

Neuroticism and CS

EM and CS

SoM and CS

Appendix (F) Model Summary, Anova and Coefficients

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.472 ^a	.223	.205	4.12703

a. Predictors: (Constant), Sense_Mattering, Extrinsic_Motivation, Performance_Orientation, Neuroticism

b. Dependent Variable: Career_Satisfaction

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	873.449	4	218.362	12.820	.000 ^b
	Residual	3048.790	179	17.032		
	Total	3922.239	183			

a. Dependent Variable: Career_Satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Sense_Mattering, Extrinsic_Motivation, Performance_Orientation, Neuroticism

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	15.911	3.088		5.153	.000
	Performance_Orientation	.068	.049	.097	1.386	.168
	Neuroticism	-.112	.024	-.337	-4.727	.000
	Extrinsic_Motivation	-.115	.091	-.087	-1.268	.206
	Sense_Mattering	.071	.022	.220	3.161	.002

a. Dependent Variable: Career_Satisfaction

Appendix (G) Residual statistics and Graphs

Statistics

Residuals Statistics^a

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	10.9960	22.6710	17.4022	2.18471	184
Residual	-11.22297	8.67352	.00000	4.08167	184
Std. Predicted Value	-2.932	2.412	.000	1.000	184
Std. Residual	-2.719	2.102	.000	.989	184

a. Dependent Variable: Career_Satisfaction

Histogram: Regression Standardised Residuals

P-P Plot Standardised Residuals and Observed Cum Prob

Scatterplot: Standardised Residuals & Standardised Predicted Values

Appendix (H) Correlations Table

		Correlations				
		Career_Satisf action	Performance _Orientation	Neuroticism	Extrinsic_Moti vation	Sense_Matter ing
Pearson Correlation	Career_Satisfaction	1.000	.038	-.398	-.143	.329
	Performance_Orientation	.038	1.000	.188	.238	.115
	Neuroticism	-.398	.188	1.000	.204	-.277
	Extrinsic_Motivation	-.143	.238	.204	1.000	-.047
	Sense_Mattering	.329	.115	-.277	-.047	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Career_Satisfaction	.	.305	.000	.026	.000
	Performance_Orientation	.305	.	.005	.001	.060
	Neuroticism	.000	.005	.	.003	.000
	Extrinsic_Motivation	.026	.001	.003	.	.265
	Sense_Mattering	.000	.060	.000	.265	.
N	Career_Satisfaction	184	184	184	184	184
	Performance_Orientation	184	184	184	184	184
	Neuroticism	184	184	184	184	184
	Extrinsic_Motivation	184	184	184	184	184
	Sense_Mattering	184	184	184	184	184

Appendix (I) Multi Regression Tests (F test and P value) & Coefficients with Collinearity Statistics

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			Sig. F Change	Durbin-Watson
						F Change	df1	df2		
1	.472 ^a	.223	.205	4.12703	.223	12.820	4	179	.000	1.927

a. Predictors: (Constant), Sense_Mattering, Extrinsic_Motivation, Performance_Orientation, Neuroticism

b. Dependent Variable: Career_Satisfaction

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations			Collinearity Statistics		
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)	15.911	3.088		5.153	.000	9.817	22.004						
	Performance_Orientation	.068	.049	.097	1.386	.168	-.029	.165	.038	.103	.091	.893	1.119	
	Neuroticism	-.112	.024	-.337	-4.727	.000	-.159	-.065	-.398	-.333	-.312	.854	1.171	
	Extrinsic_Motivation	-.115	.091	-.087	-1.268	.206	-.294	.064	-.143	-.094	-.084	.916	1.091	
	Sense_Mattering	.071	.022	.220	3.161	.002	.027	.115	.329	.230	.208	.894	1.119	

a. Dependent Variable: Career_Satisfaction

Appendix (J) Predictor Variables centred, interaction values when moderating by Neuroticism tables

PGO moderated by Neuroticism on CS

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	17.417	.318		54.842	.000	16.791	18.044
	Performance_centred	.081	.049	.115	1.668	.097	-.015	.178
	Neuroticism_Centred	-.139	.023	-.418	-6.046	.000	-.185	-.094
	Neuroticism_Performance_centred	-.001	.003	-.020	-.288	.773	-.007	.005

a. Dependent Variable: Career_Satisfaction

Regression Test

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			Sig. F Change
						F Change	df1	df2	
1	.414 ^a	.172	.158	4.24836	.172	12.438	3	180	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Neuroticism_Performance_centred, Performance_centred, Neuroticism_Centred

b. Dependent Variable: Career_Satisfaction

EM moderated by Neuroticism on CS

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	17.520	.319		54.850	.000
	Neuroticism_Centred	-.123	.023	-.369	-5.301	.000
	Extrinsic_M_centred	-.120	.093	-.092	-1.294	.197
	Neuroticism_Ext_M_Centred	-.012	.007	-.122	-1.754	.081

a. Dependent Variable: Career_Satisfaction

Regression Test

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.420 ^a	.176	.163	4.23654

a. Predictors: (Constant), Neuroticism_Ext_M_Centred, Neuroticism_Centred, Extrinsic_M_centred

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	691.558	3	230.519	12.844	.000 ^b
	Residual	3230.681	180	17.948		
	Total	3922.239	183			

a. Dependent Variable: Career_Satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Neuroticism_Ext_M_Centred, Neuroticism_Centred, Extrinsic_M_centred

SoM moderated by Neuroticism on CS

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	17.469	.316		55.350	.000	16.846	18.092
	Neuroticism_Centred	-.114	.023	-.343	-4.898	.000	-.160	-.068
	Sense_Mat_c	.073	.022	.227	3.247	.001	.029	.117
	Neur_Sense_M_c	.001	.001	.057	.837	.404	-.002	.004

a. Dependent Variable: Career_Satisfaction

Regression test

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.462 ^a	.213	.200	4.14094

a. Predictors: (Constant), Neur_Sense_M_c, Sense_Mat_c, Neuroticism_Centred

b. Dependent Variable: Career_Satisfaction

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	835.709	3	278.570	16.246	.000 ^b
	Residual	3086.530	180	17.147		
	Total	3922.239	183			

a. Dependent Variable: Career_Satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Neur_Sense_M_c, Sense_Mat_c, Neuroticism_Centred

Appendix (K) Interaction Graphs and Plots

Interaction Regression Standardised Residual Histogram
Below best fit

PGO interactions 1 Std Above and
Below best fit

SOM interactions 1 Std Above and Below best fit

EM interactions 1 Std Above and Below best fit

Appendix (L) Cronbach tests

Career Satisfaction

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.887	5

Extrinsic Motivation

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.707	4

Performance Goal Orientation

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.800	8

Sense of Mattering

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.859	12

Neuroticism

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.908	20

Appendix (T) Career Satisfaction Scale

Read the following statements and select one number for each statement to indicate how much you agree or disagree with each of the statements.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
(1) I am satisfied with the success I have achieved in my career.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(2) I am satisfied with the progress I have made towards meeting my overall career goals.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(3) I am satisfied with the progress I have made towards meeting my goals for income.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(4) I am satisfied with the progress I have made towards meeting my goals for advancement.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(5) I am satisfied with the progress I have made towards meeting my goals for the development of new skills.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Appendix (U) Sense of Mattering Scale

Read the following statements and select one number for each statement to indicate how much you agree or disagree with each of the statements.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
<i>Awareness</i>					
Most people do not seem to notice when I come or when I go	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
In a social gathering, no one recognizes me	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sometimes when I am with others, I feel almost as if I were invisible	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
People are usually aware of my presence	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
For whatever reason, it is hard for me to get other people's attention	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Whatever else may happen, people do not ignore me	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
For better or worse, people generally know when I am around	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

People tend not to remember my name

Importance

People do not care what happens to me

There are people in my life who react to what happens to me in the same way they would if it had happened to them

My successes are a source of pride to people in my life

I have noticed that people will sometimes inconvenience themselves to help me

When I have a problem, people usually don't want to hear about it

Much of the time, other people are indifferent to my needs

There are people in my life who care enough about me to criticize me when I need it

There is no one who really takes pride in my accomplishments

No one would notice if one day I disappeared

If the truth be known, no one really needs me

Reliance

Quite a few people look to me for advice on issues of importance

I am not someone people turn to when

they need
something

People tend to rely on me for support

When people need help, they come to me

People count on me to be there in times of need

Often people trust me with things that are important to them

Appendix (V) Neuroticism Scale

Read the following statements and select one number for each statement to indicate how much you agree or disagree with each of the statements as being applicable to you.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
+					
Often feel blue	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Dislike myself	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Am often down in the dumps	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Have frequent mood swings	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Panic easily	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
-					
Rarely get irritated	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Seldom feel blue	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Feel comfortable with myself	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Am not easily bothered by things	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Am very pleased with myself	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
+					
Am filled doubts about myself	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Feel threatened easily	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Get stressed out easily	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fear for the worst	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Worry about things	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
-					
Am relaxed most of the time	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Seldom get mad	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Am not easily frustrated	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Remain calm under pressure	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Rarely lose my composure	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Appendix (W) Extrinsic & Intrinsic Motivation Scale

Read the following statements and select one number for each statement to indicate how much you agree or disagree with each of the statements as being applicable to you.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Intrinsic Motivation					
The tasks that I do at work are themselves representing a driving power in my job	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The tasks that I do at work are enjoyable	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
My job is meaningful	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
My job is very exciting	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
My job is so interesting that it is a motivation in itself	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sometimes I become so inspired by my job that I almost forget	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

everything else
around me

**Extrinsic
Motivation**

If I am supposed to put in extra effort in my job, I need to get extra pay	<input type="checkbox"/>					
It is important for me to have an external incentive to strive for in order to do a good job	<input type="checkbox"/>					
External incentives such as bonuses and provisions are essential for how well I perform my job	<input type="checkbox"/>					
If I had been offered better pay, I would have done a better job	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Appendix (X) Goal Orientation Scale

Read the following statements and select one number for each statement to indicate how much you agree or disagree with each of the statements as being applicable to you.

Strongly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Slightly Agree	Strongly Agree
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working on a fairly difficult task.

I try hard to improve on my past performance.

The opportunity to extend the range of my abilities is important to me.

When I have difficulty solving a problem, I enjoy trying different approaches to see which one will work.